

SELECTION OF PRIMARY SOURCES FOR THE CREATION OF EARLY, HIGH-YIELD AND HEAT-RESISTANT EXPORT VARIETIES OF SESAME FOR THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF OUR REPUBLIC

M.E. Amanova¹, I.C. Norov²

Professor of “Vegetable Growing and Greenhouse Management” Department, TashSAU¹

Doctoral student at South Agricultural Research Institute²

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Abstract. *In the climatic conditions of Kashkadarya region, 114 varieties of sesame of the world collection were studied according to morphobiological and economic characteristics. During the researches, various directions of selection were selected, including: 5 samples for early ripening, 9 samples for productivity of one plant, 17 samples for seed size, and 33 samples for fertility.*

In the future, these samples will be used as primary sources for the creation of early, high-yielding and heat-resistant export varieties of sesame for the southern regions of our republic.

Keywords: *world collection of sesame, sample, selection, early ripening, productivity of one plant, primary material.*

It is important to suggest that the Appendix 4 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2024, PD-36, and Clause 23 of the Action Plan for the Development of the Food Industry in Uzbekistan for 2024–2028 states that in order to further develop the production of vegetable oils in the regions of the country, it is necessary to expand the areas where raw materials for vegetable oil are produced. The plan also involves identifying and distributing regions where oilseed crops can be grown based on soil and climatic conditions.

Definitely, this decree, along with ensuring Uzbekistan's food security, sets several tasks to enhance the export potential of the economy through the production of competitive products, ensure the stable supply of agricultural products at affordable prices to the population throughout the year, and increase processing capabilities. Furthermore, the decree highlights the importance of creating a raw material base to expand the production of a wide range of oil-based products and develop a healthy competitive environment.

Certainly, in order to provide the population of the Republic with a wide assortment of cheap and high-quality vegetable oils, it is essential to create new early-maturing, high-yielding, ecologically stress-resistant, and export-oriented varieties of oilseeds, establish primary and varietal seed production, and implement these in production. This is one of the pressing issues of today.

Currently, water scarcity is one of the main challenges in the country. Therefore, when implementing the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan, special attention must be given to oilseed crops that require minimal water.

In our country drought-resistant oilseed crops such as sesame, flax and mustard are mainly grown. Among these crops, sesame is considered a beneficial plant for the human body and an export-oriented crop with high demand in the global market. The two-year scientific research

conducted by us (2023-2024) contributes to the implementation of the tasks outlined in the aforementioned normative-legal documents to a certain extent.

Purpose of the research is to select primary sources for different breeding directions in the development of early-maturing, high-yielding, heat-resistant, and export-oriented sesame varieties that are suitable for the climatic conditions of the southern regions of our country.

In the research there was involved 110 sesame samples from 27 countries, collected from the Plant Genetic Resources ITI Genofund. These samples were studied for the first time under the climatic conditions of Kashkadarya region, focusing on morphological, biological and valuable agricultural traits (early maturity, productivity, large seed size, and high oil content in seeds). As a result, promising sources for various breeding directions were identified.

During the growing season, phenological observations were conducted. The growth stages of sesame samples from different origins were analyzed based on geographic regions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Seedling collection (2024)

As a standard, the Tashkent-122 variety, which is widely grown in Kashkadarya, was selected. The growth period of this variety is 119 days, with an average of 120 capsules per plant, and each capsule contains 65 seeds. Its productivity is 23.4 g, the weight of 1000 seeds is 2.7 g, and the oil content in the seeds is 49.4%.

Samples selected for early ripening characteristics from the world sesame collection. Out of the 114 samples involved in the research, 59 samples were found to ripen 4-5 days earlier compared to the standard variety, Tashkent-122. These samples come from Uzbekistan, Armenia, China, Turkey, R. Rados, Mexico, Cyprus, Korea, Egypt, Africa, Tunisia, Azerbaijan, Tajikistan, Iran, Israel, Japan, Nigeria, BADM-4, Afghanistan, and Venezuela, with a growing period of 114-115 days (Table 1).

In these samples, the number of seed pods per plant ranged from an average of 70 to 140, with 5 of them showing the same result as the standard (120 pods), 5 showing higher values (130-140 pods), and the remaining 49 having lower results compared to the standard.

Among the samples selected for early ripening characteristics, 4 samples with higher results in other valuable agricultural traits (number of seed pods per plant, number of seeds per pod, plant productivity, and oil content in seed composition) compared to the standard variety were selected. In these samples, the plant productivity ranged from 1.4 to 7.76 grams, and the oil content in the seed composition was found to be 7.1-12.71% higher (Figure 2).

Table 1

Samples selected for early ripening characteristics compared to the standard variety Tashkent-122 (2023-2024).

№	Catalog №	Origin	Growth period, days	Number of pods per plant, pcs	Number of seeds per pod	Yield per plant, g	1000 seed weight, g	Content in seed composition, %
1	Samples	Tash-122	119	120	65	23,4	2,7	49,4
2	K-4	Uzbekistan	115	90	65	16,6	2,84	41,7
3	K-15	Uzbekistan	115	90	65	14	2,4	52,3
4	K-17	Uzbekistan	115	140	70	28,4	2,9	56,5
5	K-53	Uzbekistan	115	130	65	22,6	2,68	55,5
6	K-546	Uzbekistan	114	90	65	14	2,4	44,3
7	K-76	Uzbekistan	114	90	65	16,1	2,76	39,5
8	K-77	Uzbekistan	115	90	70	16,4	2,6	40,5
9	K-275	Uzbekistan	114	130	70	28	2,4	58,4
10	K-458	Uzbekistan	114	110	65	20	2,8	40,5
11	K-139	Turkey	115	80	60	13,8	2,66	52,2
12	K-139	Turkey	115	80	60	13,8	2,66	52,2
13	K-155	Turkey	114	110	60	19	2,6	57,3
14	K-156	Turkey	115	120	65	22,5	2,6	56,5
15	K-158	Turkey	114	70	55	11,1	2,2	43,3
16	K-280	Turkey	114	120	65	24	2,6	53
17	K-162	Turkey	115	100	60	17,3	2,4	51,1
18	K-163	Turkey	115	70	55	11,1	2,4	45,3
19	K-166	Turkey	114	90	60	15,6	2,4	42,3
20	K-180	Turkey	115	100	60	17,3	2,4	55,6
21	K-184	Turkey	114	80	65	15	2,8	42,3
22	K-186	Turkey	115	100	65	18,7	2,58	45,3
23	K-281	Turkey	114	130	70	24,8	2,72	58,5
24	K-194	O.Rados	114	100	70	20,2	2,5	59,1
25	K-846	Mexico	114	90	55	11,88	2,4	44,2
26	K-848	Mexico	114	90	55	11,09	2,24	42,2
27	K-207	Mexico	114	80	65	16,02	2,54	44,3
28	K-242	Armanistan	114	100	65	18,2	2,8	43,3
29	K-97	Armanistan	115	80	60	11,52	2,4	40,5
30	K-265	Western China	115	120	65	24,02	3,1	39,5
31	K-267	Western China	115	110	60	20,33	2,2	51,9
32	K-592	China	114	90	70	19,4	2,6	45,3
33	K-249	China	114	140	70	31,16	3,18	62,11
34	K-247	O.Kipir	115	110	65	22,02	2,6	54,8

35	K-252	Korea	115	120	65	24,02	2,5	56,5
36	K-277	Egypt	117	120	70	25,87	2,8	45,6
37	K-276	Africa	114	90	55	11,88	2,4	39,5
38	K-213	Tunis	114	100	65	20,02	2,6	60,1
39	K-241	Azerbaijon	115	110	65	22,02	2,6	57,2
40	K-434	Tojikistan	115	110	65	17,16	2,4	56,2
41	K-435	BADM-4	114	100	60	15,24	2,54	42,2
42	K-826	Nigeria	114	110	70	20,56	2,67	42,5
43	K-479	Iran	115	110	65	17,16	2,4	52,8
44	K-475	Iran	115	80	60	10,08	2,1	39,5
45	K-878	Iran	115	100	60	13,2	2,2	44,2
46	K-1127	Israil	114	110	65	19,16	2,68	55,2
47	K-1134	Japan	115	80	55	9,68	2,2	52,9
48	K-727	Japan	114	110	65	18,59	2,6	45,2
49	K-761	Afghanistan	115	80	65	14,56	2,8	44,3
50	K-760	Afghanistan	115	70	55	8,47	2,2	46,3
51	K-837	Afghanistan		110	65	18,59	2,6	40,5
52	K-56	Afghanistan	115	80	55	9,68	2,2	39,5
53	K-73	Afghanistan	115	90	60	15,12	2,8	41,3
54	K-509	Turkmaniston	114	110	65	20,02	2,8	45,3
55	K-518	Turkmaniston	114	110	70	18,48	2,4	42,3
56	K-885	Venezuela	114	110	60	15,84	2,4	48,2
57	K-901	Venezuela	114	90	70	17,64	2,8	44,2
58	K-192		115	70	55	11,1	2,4	39,5
59	K-137		115	70	55	11,1	2,4	56,4
60	K-152		115	110	60	19	2,6	49,2

Figure 2. Sources selected based on early ripening characteristics from the sesame collection samples (2023-2024).

Figure 3. Southern Agricultural Scientific-Research Institute (Kashkadarya 2024).

Figure 4. Process of determining the oil content in seed composition using the Sox-406 apparatus in the Genomics Biotechnology Laboratory (2023).

One of the main factors influencing yield is the productivity of a single plant. Based on this characteristic, 9 samples, including: local k-5; k-14; k-275; k-462 (Uzbekistan), k-187 Turkey, k-202 O. Rados, k-249 China, k-303 Krasnodar, and k-472 Iran, showed higher indicators compared to other samples. The productivity of one plant in these samples ranged from 26.2 to 31.16 grams, achieving an advantage of 2.8 to 7.76 grams over the standard variety.

It is important to mention that among the selected samples based on the productivity of a single plant, the samples k-17, k-275 (Uzbekistan) and k-249 (China), which were also selected for early ripening characteristics compared to the standard variety, had a growing period of 114-115 days.

Meanwhile, the samples from Turkey, Krasnodar, O. Rados and Iran had a growing period of 120-121 days, ripening at almost the same time as the standard variety (Table 2).

In the sesame processing process, large seed size is considered one of the important quality indicators. The large seed size depends on the variety characteristics of the crop.

Therefore, large-seed, oil- and protein-rich new varieties require large-seed breeding materials. Our research noted that out of the 114 sesame samples studied, 17 samples had large seeds compared to the standard variety.

Among these samples, it is worth mentioning to highlight 4 unique sources, k-5 (Uzbekistan), k-202 (O. Rados), k-249 (China), and k-303 (Krasnodar), which have achieved superiority not only in terms of large seed size, but also in all valuable agricultural traits.

Table 2

Main valuable agricultural traits of the sesame samples selected for yield from the world collection (2023-2024).

№	Catalogue N.	Origin	Growth period	1 number of pods per plant.	Seed in the first pod	"1 plant. Yield, g."	"Weight of 1000 seeds, g."	Oil content in the seed, %.
1	St	Tash-122	119	120	65	23,4	2,7	49,4
2	K-17	Uzbekistan	115	140	70	28,4	2,90	56,5
3	K-5	Uzbekistan	120	130	70	28,2	3,10	65,8
4	K-275	Uzbekistan	114	130,0	70,0	28,0	2,40	58,4
5	K-462	Uzbekistan	122	140,0	70,0	27,8	2,84	59,6
6	K-187	Turkey	121	130,0	70,0	26,2	2,60	59,6
7	K-202	O.Rados	120	140	70	30,18	3,48	58,7
8	K-249	China	114	140	70	31,16	3,18	62,1
9	K-303	Krasnodar	120	130	70	28,03	3,24	57,4
10	K-472	Iran	120	140	70	27,44	2,80	58,9

The weight of 1000 seeds of the selected samples ranges from 3.18 grams to 3.48 grams, while this indicator for the standard variety was 2.7 grams (Table 3).

Table 3

Promising sources selected for large seed size from the world sesame collection.

№	Catalogue №	Origin	Growth period	"Number of pods per plant."	"Number of seeds in one pod."	"Yield per plant, g."	"Weight of 1000 seeds, g."	"Oil content in the seed, %."
1	St	Tash-122	119	120	65	23,4	2,7	49,40
2	K-5	Uzbekistan	120	130	70	28,2	3,10	65,80
3	K-202	O.Rados	120	140	70	30,18	3,48	58,70
4	K-249	China	114	140	70	31,16	3,18	62,11
5	K-303	Krasnodar	120	130	70	28,03	3,24	57,40

Moreover, the growth periods of these samples vary: k-249 (China) took 114 days, while k-5 (Uzbekistan), k-202 (O. Rados), and k-303 (Krasnodar) took 120 days. In terms of the number of capsules per plant, these samples were found to be 10-20 more than the standard variety Tashkent-122, and the number of seeds per capsule was 5 more. The productivity per plant ranged from 4.8 to 7.76 grams, which was higher compared to the standard variety.

The oil content of the seeds from the sesame collection samples was determined using the Sox-406 apparatus at the Genomic Biotechnology Laboratory of the South Agricultural Research Institute, using the extraction method. Of the sesame samples studied, 33 samples had an oil content of 53-62%, which was 3.6-12.6% higher compared to the standard variety (Figure 2).

These samples include 3 local samples collected during scientific expeditions, while samples from Turkey, Tunisia, Germany, and Turkmenistan were brought to the Genetic

Resources Institute Gene Bank from the All-Union Institute of Plant Breeding (VIR) in the past century, and currently from the All-Russian Institute of Plant Breeding.

Figure 5. Selected sesame samples based on oil content (2023-2024)

By summarizing it should be suggested that at present time research continues on the selected sesame samples with valuable agricultural traits and breeding work is ongoing to create high-yielding and exportable new varieties suitable for the climate of Kashkadarya region.

REFERENCES

1. M.E. Amanova. // Biological characteristics of sesame eco-groups and primary sources for breeding // Agro-Science Journal, N. 1(21), p. 31., Tashkent, 2012.
2. M.E. Amanova, A.S. Rustamov // Methodological guide for studying the global collection of oilseeds // Collection of educational-methodological materials for the youth of the Republic "Bioekosan", Tashkent, 2010., P.20.
3. Dospikhov B.A. Field experimental methodology. –M.: Kolos, 1985, P.416.
4. N.I. Bochkarev, S.G. Borodin // Recommendations on seed production of oilseeds and essential oil crops // Krasnodar, 2004.